

ISBN: 978-81-19746-57-6

A Review on Stability Enhancement in Wind Energy Distribution System Using Facts Devices

¹Ajay Singh, ²Avinash Gaurav, ³Supriya Kumari, ⁴Shailendra Pratap Singh

^{1,3,4} Faculty of Engineering and Technology, Lucknow University, Lucknow

² NSUT Delhi

E-Mail: aryans094@gmail.com, avigaurav10@gmail.com,
supriyasuman2512@gmail.com, sh1ile9dr1@gmail.com

Abstract

The load increment increases the demand for power utilization and due to this the utilization of their existing transmission system increases. Continuous and fast improvement of power electronics technology has made Flexible AC Transmission Systems (FACTS) a good concept for power system development. The UPFC is a member of the FACTS family with very attractive features and it is a solid-state controller which can be used to control active and reactive power flow in a transmission line. In this paper, the performance of one or more FACTS Devices is investigated in controlling the flow of power over the transmission line. This research deals with the simulation of a transmission line using UPFC to improve the real and reactive power flow control through a transmission line. In this paper, a Simulink Model is considered with the UPFC model to evaluate the performance of single and double transmission line systems (33/22) kV. In the simulation study, the UPFC models ease the real-time control and dynamic compensation of the AC transmission system. The simulation model is tested for single and double transmission line systems with and without the UPFC model in the MATLAB/SIMULINK environment.

Keyword: - FACTS; Wind Turbine Generator (WTG); Distributed Generations; ride-through capability; voltage sag; weak grids; wind farms.

1 Introduction

After going through various kinds of literature, it has been observed that we have to analyze two sides of the wind distribution system, The first one is using various devices to enhance the performance of the various parameters of the wind distribution system such as FACTS devices, Distributed Generations, Compensators, etc. and the second one is analyzing the performance of Wind distribution system at different values of various parameters of wind turbine generator (WTG) such as rotor angle stability, etc.

Recent Advances in Civil, Mechanical & Electrical Engineering

[DOI:10.5281/zenodo.10394491](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10394491)

ISBN: 978-81-19746-57-6

1.1 Renewable energy in India

India is one of the countries with large production of energy from renewable sources. As of 31 March 2020, 35.86% of India's installed electricity generation capacity is from renewable sources, generating 21.22% of total utility electricity in the country. In the Paris Agreement India has committed to an Intended Nationally Determined Contributions target of achieving 40% of its total electricity generation from non-fossil fuel sources by 2030. The country is aiming for an even more ambitious target of 57% of the total electricity capacity from renewable sources by 2027 in the Central Electricity Authority's strategy blueprint.[5] According to 2027 blueprint, India aims to have 275 GW from renewable energy, 72 GW of hydroelectricity, 15 GW of nuclear energy and nearly 100 GW from “other zero emission” sources.

Since 2010 the greater part of all new wind power was added outside the customary business sectors of Europe and North America, essentially determined by the proceeding with blast in China and India. Toward the finish of 2015, China had 145 GW of wind power 5 installed.

Fig 1.1 Renewable energy scenarios in India

1.2 Global Wind Scenario

Recent Advances in Civil, Mechanical & Electrical Engineering

[DOI:10.5281/zenodo.10394491](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10394491)

Share of primary energy from wind, 2018

Fig: - 1.2 Global wind scenario

Wind power is utilized on a business premise in the greater part of the apparent multitude of nations of the world.[4] By 2018, a few nations had accomplished elevated levels of wind power entrance, for example, 41% of fixed power creation in Denmark, 28% in Ireland, 24% in Portugal, 21% in Germany and 19% in Spain.[5] In November 2018 wind power age in Scotland was higher than the nation's power utilization during the month.[6] Wind a lot of overall power use toward the finish of 2018 was 4.8%, [7] up from 3.1% four years earlier.[8] In Europe, a lot of intensity age limit was 18.8% in 2018.

1.3 Wind Energy in India

The wind power age limit in India has altogether expanded lately. Starting on 29 February 2020 the complete introduced wind power limit was 37.669 GW, the fourth biggest introduced wind power limit on the planet. Wind power limit is mostly spread over the Southern, Western and Northern locales. Wind power costs in India are diminishing quickly. The leveled levy of wind power arrived at a record low of ₹2.50 (3.3 US) per kWh (with no immediate or circuitous sponsorships) during barter for wind ventures in December 2018. In December 2018, the association government reported the appropriate rules for tax-based breeze power sales to bring greater lucidity and limit the danger to the engineers 8 Wind power saw a consistent development in India for around thirty years (1985-2018). The nation

Recent Advances in Civil, Mechanical & Electrical Engineering

[DOI:10.5281/zenodo.10394491](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10394491)

ISBN: 978-81-19746-57-6

presently positions fourth on the planet in wind power, with 37.5 gigawatts (GW) of limit introduced, the vast majority of which was driven by motivators, for example, quickened devaluation and age-based installments and alluring feed-in duties (FiT). In 2015, India declared an aspiring objective of introducing 175 GW of environmentally friendly power (RE) by December 2022. Nonetheless, it agreed to a fairly unassuming objective of 60 GW to twist as the center moved to sunlight-based force. By then, the homegrown breeze industry had just developed, with an introduced limit of 25 GW.

Fig: -1.3 State-wise installed capacity of wind power

1.3.1 Wind energy production ratio

The yearly energy creation of a breeze ranch isn't equivalent to the amount of the generator nameplate appraisals increased by the all-out hours in a year since the breeze speed is variable. The limit factor of a breeze ranch is the proportion of real profitability in a year to the hypothetical greatest. The scope of the limit factor is somewhere in the range of 20 and 40%, with values at the upper finish of the reach in especially good locales. The improvement of wind power in India started during the 1990s and has essentially expanded over the most recent couple of years. Albeit a general newcomer to the breeze business contrasted and Denmark or the US, homegrown arrangement for wind power has driven India to turn into the nation with the fourth biggest introduced wind power limit on the planet. Starting on 30 June 2018 the introduced limit of wind power in India was 34,293 MW, essentially spread across

Recent Advances in Civil, Mechanical & Electrical Engineering

[DOI:10.5281/zenodo.10394491](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10394491)

ISBN: 978-81-19746-57-6

Tamil Nadu (7,269.50 MW), Maharashtra (4,100.40 MW), Gujarat (3,454.30 MW), Rajasthan (2,784.90 MW), Karnataka (2,318.20 MW), Andhra Pradesh (746.20 MW) and Madhya Pradesh (423.40 MW) Wind power represents 10% of India's absolute introduced power limit. India has set a driven objective to produce 60,000 MW of power from wind power by 2022. 10 The Indian Government's Ministry of New and Renewable Energy declared another breeze sun-powered mixture strategy in May 2018. This implies that a similar land parcel will be utilized to house both breeze ranches and sun-oriented boards.

Fig: -1.6 wind energy production ratio

2. Power System Stability

2.1 Introduction

Force framework designing structures is a huge and significant segment of electrical designing examinations. It is essentially worried about the creation of electrical force and its transmission from the sending end to the accepting end according to prerequisites, causing a base measure of misfortunes.

The force regularly changes because of the variety of burdens or because of unsettling influences. Hence, the term power framework soundness is of most extreme significance in this field. It is utilized to characterize the capacity of the framework to bring back its activity to a consistent state condition inside a base conceivable time after having gone through any fleetingness or unsettling influence. Thus, for a steady activity, we need to synchronize the transport with the generators over the whole span of age and transmission. Thus, the force framework steadiness is likewise alluded to as simultaneous dependability and is characterized as the capacity of the framework to re-visitation of synchronism after having gone through some unsettling influence because of turning on and off of burden or because of line brevity.

2.2 Rotor angle stability

The framework can stay in synchronism when exposed to an aggravation". The rotor point of a generator relies upon the harmony between the electromagnetic force because of the generator's electrical force yield and mechanical force because of the info mechanical force through a main player. Staying in synchronism implies that all the generators choose magnetic force is equivalent to the mechanical force the other way. On the off chance that in a generator the harmony among electromagnetic and mechanical force is upset, because of aggravations in the framework, at that point this will prompt motions in the rotor point. Rotor point dependability is additionally arranged into little unsettling influence point strength and huge aggravation point steadiness.

3. Taxonomical Review

Recent Advances in Civil, Mechanical & Electrical Engineering

[DOI:10.5281/zenodo.10394491](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10394491)

ISBN: 978-81-19746-57-6

3.1 Tabular Form Review on Stability Enhancement in Wind Energy Distribution System Using Facts Devices

S. No	Name of Authors	Title	Optimizati on technique	Parameter whose performance is improved	Publication
1.	Allan Mullane, et. al.	Wind-Turbine Fault Ride-Through Enhancement	Feedback linearization control	Load current and network voltage level	IEEE Transactions on Power System
2.	M. F. Farias, et. al.	Wind Farms in Weak Grids Enhancement of Ride-Through Capability Using Custom Power Systems	Active power compensati on strategy	Voltage levels	IEEE Access
3.	J. Morel, et. al.	Energy Capacitor System for DFIG-based Wind Farm Transient Behaviour Enhancement	Fuzzy logic control	Reduced speed oscillations	IEEE T&D Asia 2009
4.	Abdelaziz Salah Saidi, et. al.	Enhancement of the Dynamic Behaviour of the Low Voltage Ride-Through Wind Turbines	Artificial Neural network	The voltage profile is improved	The 9th International Renewable Energy Congress (IREC 2018)
5.	I. Ngamroo, et. al	Stabilization of Tie-Line Power Oscillations by Robust SMES in Interconnected Power Systems with Large Wind Farms	Particle Swarm Optimizatio n	Improvement in Power system oscillations	IEEE T&D Asia 2009

6.	Babak Badrzadeh, et. al	Assessment and Enhancement of Grid Faultinduced Torsional Oscillations for Induction Generator-based Wind Turbines	Minor Control Loop (MCL) strategy	damping of torsional oscillations	2009 IEEE/PES Power Systems Conference and Exposition
7.	N. K. Roy, et. al.	An Effective VAR Planning to Improve Dynamic Voltage Profile of Distribution Networks with Distributed Wind Generation	Dynamic voltage stability	The voltage profile is improved	2012 IEEE Power and Energy Society General Meeting
8.	Khaled Saleh Banawair, et. al.	DFIG Wind-Turbine Modeling with Reactive Power Control Integrated to Large Distribution Network	Reactive Power Control Strategies	The voltage profile is improved	2014 IEEE International Conference Power & Energy (PECON)
9.	Nattapol Hapunala, et al.	Improvement of Low Voltage Ride-through Capability of DFIG-based Wind Turbines under Low Voltage Conditions	Particle Swarm Optimization	The low voltage profile is improved.	The 2019 International Electrical Engineering Congress (Ieecon2019)
10.	Anirban Chowdhury, et. al.	Optimal allocation of wind-based DG for enhancement of technical, economic & social benefits using Cuckoo Search Algorithm for radial distribution network	Cuckoo Search algorithm	Active Power losses are reduced	International Conference on Computer, Electrical & Communication Engineering (ICCECE)
11.	Yu Zhao, et al.	Stability Enhancement in Distribution Systems with DFIG-Based Wind Turbine by Use of SFCL	Particle Swarm optimization	Voltage sag, reactive power and active power are improved	Australasian Universities Power Engineering Conference,

ISBN: 978-81-19746-57-6

					AUPEC 2013, Hobart, TAS, Australia, 29 September - 3 October 2013
12.	YULY D. BAY, et al.	Stochastic modeling of a DFIG wind turbine in Matpower	Optimal Power Flow	Active power and reactive power are enhanced	IEEE ACCESS

References

[1] Narain G.Hingorani, “Role of FACTS in a Deregulated Market”; IEEE Conf.; 2000; page(s): 1463-1467.

[2] Loi Lei Lai; “Power System Restructuring and Deregulation”; JOHN WILEY & SONS, LTD; 2003.

[3] Lorrin Philipson and H.Lee Willis, Understanding Electric Utilities and De-Regulation, Marcell Dekker Inc., New York, 1999.

[4] E.J.De Oliveira, J.W.M.Lima and J.L.R. Pereira; “Flexible AC Transmission Devices: Allocation and Transmission Pricing”, Electrical power and Energy System 21; 1999; pp. 111-118.

[5] J. W. Marangon Lima and E. J. de Oliveira, “The long-term impact of transmission pricing,” IEEE Trans. Power Syst., vol. 13, no. 4, Nov. 1998, pp. 1514–1520.

[6] Yamaguchi, N.; Takahashi, I.; Kita, H.; Nishiya, K.; Hasegawa, J.; “An allocation of wheeling costs in power systems with FACTS devices”; Electric Utility Deregulation and Restructuring and Power Technologies, 2000. Proceedings; DRPT 2000. International Conference on, 4-7 April 2000; pp. 549 - 553.

[7] Srivastava, S.C. and Verma, R.K.; “Impact of FACTS devices on transmission pricing in a deregulated electricity market”; Electric Utility Deregulation and Restructuring and Power Technologies; 2000. Proceedings. DRPT 2000. International Conference on; 4-7 April 2000; pp. 642 -648.

[8] Padhy, N.P., Abdel-Moamen, M.A.R.; Trivedi, P.K.; Das, B.; “A hybrid mode for Optimal power flow incorporating FACTS devices”; Power Engineering Society Winter Meeting, 2001. IEEE, Volume: 2, 28 Jan.-1 Feb. 2001; pp. 510 -515.

Recent Advances in Civil, Mechanical & Electrical Engineering

[DOI:10.5281/zenodo.10394491](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10394491)

ISBN: 978-81-19746-57-6

- [9] J. Y. Choi, S.-H. Rim, and J.-K. Park, "Optimal real time pricing of real and reactive powers," *IEEE Trans. Power Syst.*, vol. 3, no. 4, Nov. 1998, pp. 1226–1231.
- [10] K. S. Verma, S. N. Singh, and H. O. Gupta, "Optimal location of UPFC for congestion management," *Elect. Power Syst. Res.*, vol. 58, no. 2, Jul. 2001, pp. 89–96. 70
- [11] S.N.Singh and A.K. David, "A new approach for placement of facts devices in open power markets," *IEEE Power Eng. Rev*, sept. 2001, pp. 58-60.
- [12] M. Noroozian, L. Angquist, M. Ghandhari, and G. Andersson, "Use of UPFC for optimal power flow control," *IEEE Trans. Power Delivery*, vol. 12, pp. 1629–1633, Oct. 1997.
- [13] R.K. Nema, Gayatri Agnihotri, "Power flow control with UPFC in power transmission system" *World academy of science, engineering and technology* 2008. pp. 338-342.
- [14] Douglas J. Gotham, G. T. Heydt "power flow control and power flow studies for systems with facts devices" *IEEE Trans.on power systems*, vol 13, no. 1, February 1998, pp. 60-65.
- [15] Salah Kamel, Mamdouh Abdel-Akher, and Mohamed K. "Direct Modeling of UPFC in Newton Raphson Power flow Analysis Based on Current Injections" *Proceedings of the 14th International Middle East Power Systems Conference (MEPCON'10)*, Cairo University, Egypt, December 19-21, 2010, pp. 769-774